

INDUCTION TO TEACHING PROGRAM IN TURKEY: ATTAINMENTS OF NOVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract:

With the purpose of examining and identifying the attainments of novice teachers from in-class, in-school, and out-of-school activities during the process of being a novice teacher, in accordance with the views of novice teachers, mentor teachers, and administrators; this research is a qualitative research with a phenomenological design. The data of the study were collected through semi-structured interviews with 40 novice teachers, 43 mentor teachers and 5 school administrators. Content analysis was done in the analysis of the data. As a result of the research, it can be said that there are attainments related to teaching-learning process and non-scheduled activities within the scope of in-class applications; attainments related to work and operations of schools, and duties and responsibilities of the school administration within the scope of in-school activities; and as for out-of-school activities, attainments such as familiarization with relevant institutions, organizations and people, acknowledgement of the city culture, and sharing of knowledge and experiences with experienced people stand out as themes.

Keywords: induction to teaching program, mentoring, novice teacher, mentor teacher

1. Introduction

Teachers are the primary human resources for the efficient and effective operation of the educational organizations. Improvement of teachers will increase the success of educational organizations. Nature and quality of the education are directly related to vocational proficiency levels and education of the teachers (Ekinci, 2010; Fullan, 2007; Şişman, 2001). Therefore, a significant amount of resources must be allocated to constant education and improvement of teaching staff in modern educational

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institutions (Vemić, 2007). This resource allocation is particularly used for the purpose of in-service training of teachers in educational organizations.

In-service training is a set of planned educational activities with the purpose of systematic attainment of knowledge, skills and behaviors which are required by their profession by teachers, within the period of time that starts when individuals start working and ends when they stop working (Aytaç, 2000; Taymaz, 1997; Can, Akgün and Kavuncubaşı, 1995). The rapid changes in science and technology, the paradigm shifts in the area of learning and teaching, the differentiation of the skills expected from education, the changing social expectations and necessities have obligated teachers to be in constant change and development, and the importance of in-service training has increased steadily (Selimoğlu and Yılmaz, 2009; Şişman, 2001; Saban; 2000). In this context, in-service training started to fulfill functions such as job orientation of individuals, and preparing them for new situations by refreshing their knowledge and skills (Kayabaş, 2008).

Induction to teaching is the initial in-service training activity held in educational organizations for teachers (Aydın, 2011; Çevikbaş, 2002; Taymaz, 1997). Induction to teaching is seen as an important requirement after pre-service training because there is a constant improvement in the education and training process, and the novice teacher is about to start working with great responsibilities in a new institution which he or she is a stranger to. Induction training actually provides some additional knowledge, skills and attitudes to the teachers on top of what they have learned in the pre-service training, and includes certain applications at the same time (Boyras, 2007; Özönay, 2004; Ataklı, 1992). Novice teaching period is labeled as the most difficult period of the profession (Balci, 2000; Hoy and Woolfolk, 1990), and novice teachers face many problems in this period such as classroom management, motivation of the students, individual problems of the students, inconsistency between theory and practice, cooperation with the parents, and adapting to the profession and the school (Yeşilyurt and Karakuş, 2011; Korkmaz, Saban and Akbaşlı, 2004; Yalçınkaya, 2002). Therefore, it can be said that induction training is important for novice teachers to cope with aforementioned problems and adapt to the profession.

Until 2016, induction to teaching programs in Turkey was executed in three phases, which are primary training, preparatory training and applied training, as it was specified in no. 2423 of official bulletin on 30.01.1995. Primary training involved the training about common traits and qualities of public officers; preparatory training involved the training about classes and duties of service to which novice teachers are assigned; and applied training involved the internship that was exercised by novice teachers relating to their classes and duties of service (MEB, 1995).

The duration of primary training was organized not to be less than a total of 50 hours of programs. Atatürk's principles, Turkish Republic Constitution, state organization in general, public servants law, correspondence rules and filing procedures, preservation of government property and savings measures, public relations, confidentiality and importance of confidentiality, revolution history, national security information, and Turkish grammar rules were presented within a content, as

part of this training (MEB, 1995). Preparatory training was a secondary training which started after primary training and was organized not to be less than a total of 110 hours of programs. Ministry organization, subjects related to duties of the novice teacher and other subjects deemed appropriate by the central education management board were included in this training (MEB, 1995). Candidates were required to score 60 at the least in the exams held by the end of both programs. As for applied training, they were expected to fulfill all kinds of obligations related to teaching (that was specified in detail in the regulations), not to be less than 220 hours of programs. Again in accordance with the regulations, the novice teacher was assigned in his/her own field, to a school where there is at least one teacher who is qualified as a school counselor and where there are resources (course materials etc.) related to his/her field. Novice teachers were obligated to attend all kinds of courses, seminars, conferences and other educational activities that they were assigned to through teacher's board meetings held at the school they are employed at. Again, in accordance with the regulations, teachers may not independently assume watch duty, attends classes while escorted by the school counselor, and may not deliver lessons on their own (MEB, 1995). However, during the application period of that regulation, it was a known fact that novice teachers were attending classes on their own. In the evaluation of applied training of the novice teacher, regulation-specified evaluation form was filled by two separate registry chiefs. Novices who scored 60 points at the least completed their induction periods and training with success. (MEB, 1995).

In the studies conducted related to the training of novice teachers, novice teachers stated that they find the course contents presented within supplementary and preparatory training boring, they have already encountered the presented content through their educational lives, they see the repetition of these subjects as a waste of time, they do not get practical knowledge that will fulfill their needs within the lessons, they cannot find clear answers and solutions to their professional problems, and current issues of education and the profession were not discussed adequately. In addition, views of novice teachers regarding the induction period included inconvenience of their training environments, inadequacy of qualifications of the trainers and the unnecessary stress caused by exams. (Okutan ve Aydoğdu, 2009; Özonay, 2004; Kocadağ, 2001; Yıldırım, 1997). Despite the deficiencies identified within the scope of these studies, training of novice teachers was maintained in a similar manner over the years.

According to the Ministry of National Education's Regulations on Assignment and Transfer published on the 29329 no. official bulletin on the date of 17 April 2015, it was considered appropriate that novice teachers would undergo an education period during the first term that they were appointed (MEB, 2016a). During the second term assignments of February 2016, assigned teacher candidates did not assume duty immediately, made a second choice, and assigned to the province in which they would get their induction training. As a result of the work carried out in the Provincial Directorates of National Education, they started to work in the first week of March 2016 with the mentor teachers in the schools where they will complete their induction training.

According to this new practice, novice teachers undergo a training period in the first six months of their candidacy. In accordance with the training program determined by the Ministry, the training process takes place in educational institutions, under the responsibility of the administrator and mentor teachers of the relevant institution. Within the scope of this program, novice teachers are required to perform some in-class, in-school and out-of-school activities and attend in-service activities. Independent lesson and watch duties are not assigned to the novice teacher in this process. They attend classes together with their mentor teachers, and observe their mentor teachers on watch duty (MEB, 2016a).

The training program to be applied to novice teachers during the training period, is prepared by the Directorate General for Teacher Training and Improvement. The program consists of in-school, in-class and out-of-school activities and in-service training applications.

Concerning in-class, in-school and out-of-school activities; it is targeted for novice teachers to get informed about preparation, teaching and evaluation processes of the lesson, to observe the process of preparing and using course materials and to participate in this process, to recognize problematic areas related to teaching-learning process and to develop ideas towards their solutions, to get informed about operation of educational environments and management processes, to be familiarized with implementation processes of in-school educational activities and social cultural activities, to be familiarized with the educational environment and social structure of the assigned location, to get informed about stakeholder institutions partaking in education and training processes and their operations, to realize the importance of vocational development and sharing of educational experiences, to be aware of social responsibility projects and voluntary activities, and to attain the skill of preparing monitoring and evaluation reports on education and training processes and out-of-school activities (MEB, 2016b).

Novice teachers are expected to be present at the school four (4) days a week for 16 weeks within the scope of in-school and in-class activities in order to realize these determined targets. This period equals to a total of 64 working days or 384 hours over 16 weeks. During this period, in-school observation/implementation for one (1) day each week, in-class course monitoring and implementation activities for three (3) days each week are required. Novice teachers attend lesson preparation, planning, material preparation and monitoring activities for 3 days each week and 6 hours a day for the first 6 weeks, under the guidance of their mentor teachers. For the next 10 weeks, the novice teacher performs lesson preparation, planning, material preparation and lecture giving activities for 3 days a week and 6 hours a day. In-school activities are projected as 1 day a week and a total of 96 course hours through 16 weeks. The training program will be held through a total of 16 weeks/79 days/474 hours. In this context, the novice teacher will perform activities such as lesson planning/preparation/evaluation, course monitoring, course implementation, and in-school observations and implementations (MEB, 2016b).

In order to realize the determined targets, a total of 90 hours of work is projected for one day each week and six hours a day over 15 weeks within the scope of out-of-school activities. Within the scope of out-of-school activities, the novice teacher is expected to perform works titled City Identification, Institutional Operation; The School Right Beside Us, Meeting with Experience, Volunteering and Entrepreneurship Works, and Vocational Development and Career, and also to read 5 books and watch 10 movies (MEB, 2016b).

In in-service training applications, the second phase of the training program, teacher candidates are expected to develop a sense of belonging and commitment while comprehending the mission of the teaching profession, to be aware of the educational understanding at the heart of Turkish culture and civilization, to adopt national, ethical, humane, moral and cultural values specified in the Basic Law of National Education No. 1739, to realize our cultural diversity and its relation to education, to develop knowledge and skills towards teaching applications, to know general policies and current priorities and applications of the National Education, to comprehend model applications related to learning processes and educational activities, to be informed about Turkey's educational perspective in the light of international developments and to know basic subjects in the relevant legislation about education and training. After 16 weeks of in-school and out-of-school activities, novice teachers will be attending 8 weeks (240 hours) of in-service educational activities. In this process, they will be trained in accordance with a detailed content on attainments purposed by the program (MEB, 2016b).

As a result of the study conducted by Yeşilyurt and Karakuş (2011) in order to determine the problems encountered by teachers through their candidacy periods, novice teachers have stated and were determined to face problems mostly on the subjects of adaptation to the profession and the school, not being able to receive sufficient guidance and support, inadequate in-service training, and the difference between their undergraduate education and implementation. It can be said that the induction program in the early years of the profession has great importance in order to overcome these issues. Provided induction program must be questioned in this context. There are many studies conducted with this purpose in the national and international literature.

According to Duke, Karson and Wheeler (2006), induction programs increase the commitment to the profession of teaching. Ingersoll and Strong (2011) have stated that students of the teachers who participated in the induction to teaching program have higher academic success, and these teachers have demonstrated better performance on scales such as creating a positive classroom environment and classroom management. Gujarati (2012) approaches well designed induction to teaching programs within the context of lifelong learning, and stated that these programs will provide persistence in vocational preparation and maintenance of teachers. According to Moir (2009), induction to teaching programs increase teacher contribution to student success, and enables teachers for attaining leadership skills. According to Abu Rass (2010),

applications performed during induction to teaching programs help teacher candidates evaluate student success.

After the induction to teaching program started to be implemented in Turkey, it has been the subject of many studies in the literature most of which focused on attainments of novice teachers in this process, problems encountered and solution suggestions. In their studies conducted with novice teachers; Gül, Türkmen and Aksel (2017) have stated that school administrators view induction to teaching program positively, novice teachers mostly receive guidance on class management from mentor teachers along with several indirect attainments, and certain problems were encountered in the process. In a study conducted by Gökulu (2017), it was found that that novice teachers had positive views about induction to teaching program process, they developed an awareness of student behaviors and attitudes towards the teacher via this training, and they stated that it contributed to their personal and vocational development. In their study conducted with novice teachers who attended the induction to teaching program throughout Turkey; İlyas, Coşkun and Toklucu (2017) observed that more than half of the novice teachers evaluate this training positively in terms of professional preparation and vocational development, but they also stated that it could be conducted more effectively. In the research conducted with novice teachers by Ulubey (2017), it was determined that in-class observations, in-school and out-of-school applications, suggested books and movies have all been helpful in adapting to the profession and development of vocational knowledge and skills. In a study also conducted with novice teachers by Nayır and Kuru - Çetin (2017), it was emphasized that this training is useful and that it should be continued with some corrections. In their research conducted with novice and mentor teachers along with school administrators, Tunçbilek and Tünay (2017) have determined the skills that can be attained by novice teachers in this process as, respectively, responsibility and self-development, planning, attaining the skills of teaching and class management, attaining the skill of good communication with colleagues and administrators, and attaining the skills of technology and student centeredness. In the research conducted by Sarıkaya, Samancı and Yılar (2017), findings indicated that the induction to teaching program process has contributed to novice teachers in terms of self-confidence, class management, planning, material design, educational program, communication and interaction. In their research conducted with novice teachers, mentor teachers, and school administrators, Kozikoğlu and Soyalp (2018) have determined that novice teachers attain skills from the program, such as preparing for the profession by gaining experience, learning administrative affairs and in-school operations, communicating with teachers and parents, and getting familiarized with relevant provincial institutions.

Induction to Teaching Program is applied as a new model in the training of novice teachers in Turkey. In-depth examination of this program in the context of the attainments it has provided to novice teachers and in accordance with the views of participants will provide directive and regulatory data for future applications. In this context, upon examination of the conducted research, it is evident that the studies were

mostly carried out with novice teachers, and all the other stakeholders were only included in a small number of studies. This research is significant in that it presents the attainments provided to novice teachers by the induction to teaching program comparing the opinions of all stakeholders.

In this context, this study aims to examine the attainments of novice teachers from in-class, in-school, and out-of-school activities in the progress of being a novice teacher, in accordance with opinions of novice teachers, mentor teachers, and administrators. To this end, answers to the following questions were searched:

1. About the attainments provided by in-class implementations during the process of being a novice teacher;
2. About the attainments provided by in-school implementations during the process of being a novice teacher;
3. About the attainments provided by out-of-school implementations during the process of being a novice teacher;
 - What are the views of the novice teachers?
 - What are the views of the mentor teachers?
 - What are the views of the school administrators?

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

The study used the phenomenological design among qualitative research designs. Phenomenology is interested in real experiences (Merriam, 2009). This research design aims to reveal individual perceptions, perspectives and common applications about a certain phenomenon, and to identify, explain and interpret the meanings created by the participants (Annells, 2006; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008, Cresswell, 2013). This research aims to examine the attainments of novice teachers from in-class, in-school and out-of-school activities during the process of induction, in accordance with opinions of novice teachers, mentor teachers, and administrators. Accordingly, the phenomenon determined within the scope of the research is the phenomenon of "induction to teaching". Towards this phenomenon, the comprehension and the evaluation of experiences of the novice teachers who underwent the training and the mentor teachers responsible for providing the training and the school administrators, again through their own opinions.

2.2 The Study Group

In phenomenological research, the data sources are individuals or groups who are focused on by the research and who can externally reflect on this phenomenon (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008). This research study group consisted of 40 novice teachers, 43 mentor teachers who acted as consultants to the novice teachers, and 5 school administrators who work as administrators in the same schools as these novice and mentor teachers. In the forming of the study group, interviews were conducted with volunteers from the aforementioned groups. Moreover, teachers who are working in

elementary, middle, and high schools were preferred in the selection of novice and teachers who were interviewed with. 10 novice teachers, 10 mentor teachers and one school administrator from elementary schools; 17 novice teachers, 17 mentor teachers and 3 school administrators from middle schools; and 13 novice teachers, 16 mentor teachers and one school administrator from high schools were interviewed with. Branches of the novice teachers and the mentor teachers consist of 18 branches such as class, technology design, music, English, special education, social studies, science, religious culture and moral knowledge, counseling, information technologies, Turkish, geography, Turkish philology, electricians, electronics, industrial automation, furnishing, interior design, and mathematics. Lengths of service of the mentor teachers vary between 11 to 38 years. Only 16 of the novice teachers have already had some teaching experience. Two of the school administrators work as school principals, and three of them as vice principals.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews within the scope of the research. To this end, the researchers used interview forms prepared exclusively for novice teachers, mentor teachers and school administrators.

While preparing semi-structured interview forms, relevant sections of the "Induction to Teaching Program" (MEB, 2016b) prepared by the National Ministry of Education's Directorate General for Teacher Training and Improvement and the National Ministry of Education's No. 29329 Teacher Assignment and Transfer Regulations (MEB, 2016a) published on the official gazette on the date of 17 April 2015 were examined, and questions in the interview forms were developed as a result of these examinations. The form developed was initially presented to three experts in the field, revised in the light of their feedback, and then pilot interviews were conducted with a novice teacher, a mentor teacher, and a school administrator. During the pilot interviews, questions that came out to be unclear were identified and interview forms were finalized as a result of the feedback from interviewees about how to ask these questions.

Required official consent was received from the relevant National Education Directorate in the collection of data. Receiving consent from and signing contracts with participants are required for video/audio recording and the collection of research data in qualitative studies. To this aim, contracts were signed with the participants.

2.4 Collection of the Data

Data were collected by audio-recorded semi-structured interviews via forms developed by the researcher. Participants' consent was obtained prior to each interview regarding the sound recording. The interviews were conducted on school libraries, science laboratories and assembly halls depending on the physical conditions of the school. Interviews lasted for 15 - 35 minutes.

2.5 Analysis of the Data

Audio recordings were initially transferred to written media in the analysis of the data. Accuracy of the transferred data was checked by an expert. Content analysis was done in the analysis of the data. The data were individually examined by the researcher with the help of Nvivo 9 packaged software, properly coded and themed, and then presented to another field expert for independent coding and theming for reliability analysis. As a result of the reliability analysis, a consensus was reached at the level of 81, and it was concluded that the data were reliably analyzed (Miles and Huberman, 1998).

3. Results

As a result of the analyses made, findings are presented under three main titles. These main titles will be presented respectively as; Findings Related to Novice Teacher Opinions, Findings Related to Mentor Teacher Opinions, and Findings Related to School Administrator Opinions.

3.1 Findings Related to Novice Teacher Opinions

In the analysis of the data obtained as a result of semi-structured interviews conducted with novice teachers; presentation of the data was carried out under three titles which are attainments from in-class applications, attainments from in-school applications and attainments from out-of-school applications.

3.1.1 Attainments from In-Class Applications

Within the scope of in-class applications, the novice teachers indicated that they have attainments related to the learning-teaching process, non-scheduled activities and social relations. The data related to these attainments can be seen in Chart 1.

Chart 1: Attainments from In-Class Applications

Attainments Related to Learning-Teaching Process
Receiving feedback on teaching processes
Managing the teaching process
Technology use in teaching
Field information support
Use of different methods - techniques
Information on teaching tools and equipment
Practical application
Classroom Management
Communication with the student

Attainments Related to Non-Scheduled Activities

Club activities
 Class trip organization
 Communication with parents
 Social event organization
 PTA meetings
 Group teachers meetings
 Class counseling
 Project preparation

Attainments Related to Social Relations

Attainments related to the teaching-learning process were stated as follows; receiving feedback about the learning processes, managing the teaching process, technology use in teaching, field information support, use of different methods - techniques, Information on teaching tools and equipment, practical application, classroom management, and communication with the student. Following statement was given about receiving feedback about the learning processes by NT4; *"(He/she) tells me if I lack anything about how to teach lessons and also my good sides. I ask (him/her) about what activities can be done on this subject or how to teach the lessons before classes, because (he/she) is an experienced person."* Also, NT40 stated the following about class management; *"(He/she) informed me about how to stand in the classroom and how to manage the classroom."*

They pointed out that their attainments related to non-scheduled activities include club activities, organizing class trips, communication with parents, group teachers meetings, PTA meetings, and project preparation. About the watch duty, NT1 stated; *"(He/she) sometimes tells me what to do during watch duty. Gives certain information to me such as to take statements down if any problems occur during watch duty, to keep the doors constantly open, to intervene with the student immediately in case of danger, to look after them..."*. And NT24 stated the following about organizing social events; *"For example, we have prepared for 19 May celebrations last week in our school. ...We conduct its flow, editing and checking of the poetry etc."*

3.1.2 In-School Activities and Attainments

The sub-themes under the theme of In-School Activities and Attainments are shown in Chart 2.

Chart 2: In-School Activities and Attainments

Administrator tasks
E-school
Use of Ministry of National Education (MNE) Data Processing Systems
Social Event Organization
Surtitle Writing
EBA and FATİH Projects
Duties of the guidance service
Giving permission slips
Disciplinary board works
Not Helpful

Novice teachers expressed that they had attainments from in-school activities, on subjects such as administrative tasks, e-school system, use of MNE data processing systems, social event organization, surtitle writing, EBA and FATİH projects, duties of the guidance service, giving permission slips, and disciplinary board works. NT14 gave information about learning works and operation of the school administration and official correspondence rules by stating the following; *"correspondence, kind of works done by the principal and especially vice principals, their distribution of work in accordance with their own fields, ...Gives permission slips about giving permission to students when they come. ... In the news coming from the Provincial Directorate of National Education, we saw how they arrived as correspondences, how they were printed out, what must be done in the proceeding processes and so on. We did a lot in MNE Data Processing Systems. We submitted our own information on it. Our teacher helped us there about exam applications etc. We have helped with these types of correspondence procedures."*

Some novice teachers have expressed that they did not attain anything from in-school activities. A novice teacher, who thinks that activities were not helpful, stated the following: NT19 - *"I can't say it's very efficient. Ultimately, you observe, you observe the relation of the school administrator with parents etc. So when we observe for 16 weeks, we can also communicate with parents. Observing one time is enough. Actually, I think we can learn better if we were to be on the field about this..."*

3.1.3 Out-of-School Activities and Attainments

The sub-themes under the theme of Out-of-School Activities and Attainments are shown in Chart 3.

Chart 3: Out-of-School Activities and Attainments

Different Institutions and Organizations
Science and Arts Center
Directorate of National Education
Public Education Center
Guidance Research Center
District Governorship
Meeting with Experience
City Trips

Within the scope of out-of-school activities, they expressed that they have visited institutions such as science and arts center, directorate of national education, public education center, guidance research center, and district governorship; they went on city trips and interviewed retired teachers within the scope of meeting with experience activities. Novice teacher NT14 stated the following while expressing the attainments from out-of-school activities *"I liked BİLSEM the most in the scope of these out-of-school activities. Because I didn't know, a place like this existed. With this, I have seen that I must observe students much better. Not only teaching the class, but I also have to follow up on the skills of the child better, and see what level he/she is on."* NT37 stated the following *"We met up with retired teachers last week. What they shared were very nice. People who retired*

alongside new graduates. Quite frankly, we have seen ourselves in 30-40 years. Like, what we would encounter in that process. That was very efficient. We went to District National Education and Provincial National Education. We have learned about the rights of the teacher, what to do about operations, our responsibilities... Because we unavoidably have connections to there. We learned about them. We know where to apply to, what unit to communicate with when we encounter a problem.", while expressing that he/she was influenced by meeting with experience activities particularly, and that it was helpful to obtain information about where to apply in case of a problem.

3.2 Findings Related to Mentor Teacher Opinions

In the analysis of the data obtained as a result of semi-structured interviews conducted with mentor teachers; presentation of the data was carried out under three titles which are attainments from in-class applications, attainments from in-school applications and attainments from out-of-school applications.

3.2.1 Attainments from In-Class Applications

Within the scope of in-class applications, the mentor teachers indicated that they have attainments related to the learning-teaching process, out-of-school activities and social relations. The data related to these attainments can be seen in Chart 3.

Sub-themes under the theme of Mentor Teacher Guidance can be seen in Chart 4.

Chart 4: Attainments from In-Class Applications (Opinions of Mentor Teachers)

Attainments Related to Learning-Teaching Process Communication with the student Classroom Management Material design Exam preparation Feedbacks on teaching processes Teaching processes Examination of the curriculum Materialization of the subjects to be learned Considering individual differences Technology use in teaching Plan preparation Giving homework Completing deficiencies in field knowledge Evaluation of the project tasks
Attainments Related to Non-Scheduled Activities Social event organization Preparing group reports Holding PTA meetings Watch duty Attending the meetings of the branch teachers board Performing class counseling Performing club works Filling class books Getting informed about the counseling service Performing in-school maintenance and repair services

Getting informed about problems that might be encountered by vocational teachers in workshops

Attainments Related to Social Relations

Getting informed about the problems that may be encountered in the teaching profession

Giving feedback towards educating teachers

Ability to share information with colleagues

About the attainments towards the learning-teaching process, they have mentioned subjects such as communication with the student, classroom management, material design, exam preparation, receiving feedback about teaching processes, teaching processes, examination of the curriculum, materialization of the subjects to be learned, considering individual differences, technology use in teaching, plan preparation, giving homework, completing deficiencies in field knowledge, and evaluation of project tasks. About communication with students, MT27 stated the following to describe the attainments of the novices; *"I think I have guided the novice in the class, in group activities, about controlling the class, communicating with the class, body language, stance, and communicating with young people."* MT25 stated the following; *"I have shared the tools, equipment, and materials we have been preparing for years with my novice."*, while talking about the attainments he/she tried to provide to his/her novice teacher about material design.

About attainments related to non-scheduled activities, they have stated that there are attainments on social event organization, preparing group reports, attending branch teachers' board meetings, performing club works, filling class books, getting informed about the counseling service, performing in-school maintenance and repairs services, getting informed about problems that might be encountered by vocational teachers in workshops. MT33 stated the following; *"Library week was in March. I assigned my novice teacher to library week..... I provided my documents and information to him/her about celebration of holidays, special days and weeks. For him/her to examine and to see how it was prepared."* in order to express his/her efforts of guidance towards the novice teacher on the subject of organizing social events.

As for the attainments related to social relations, they have stated that the novice teachers have attainments in the sub-themes of getting informed on problems they may encounter on the teaching profession, giving feedback towards educating teachers, and ability to share knowledge with colleagues.

3.2.2 In-School Activities and Attainments

The sub-themes under the theme of In-School Activities and Attainments are shown in Chart 5.

Chart 5: In-School Activities and Attainments

Recognition of school administration's work and operation
Learning of communication between the school administration and the teachers
E-school procedures
Student affairs
Supporting the teacher identity
Preparing decimal files
Disciplinary board works
Learning of personal rights
Arrangement of student internships
Counseling and club works
Social event organization

About in-school activities that were performed by novice teachers, mentor teachers have stated that there are attainments such as recognition of school administration's work and operation, learning of communication between the school administration and the teachers, e-school procedures, student affairs, supporting the teacher identity, preparing decimal files, disciplinary board works, learning of personal rights, arrangement of student internships, counseling and club works, and social event organization. MT18 stated the following; *"So there were massive informative efforts primarily about administrative works. They observed and followed up on several administrative works such as how to prepare a syllabus or what their personal rights are"*, while reporting that novice teachers learned both about work and operation of school administration and their own personal rights. MT21 stated the following; *"Adaptation to work. They get close to the kitchen of the business, to begin with. We all perceive them as teachers. They all work in administration; they have visited national education units, which of course contributes to them in terms of teacher identity. Their self-confidence is very different now"* in order to express that in-school activities supported the teacher identity.

3.2.3 Out-of-School Activities and Attainments

The sub-themes under the theme of Out-of-School Activities and Attainments are shown in Chart 6.

Chart 6: Out-of-School Activities and Attainments

Beneficial and necessary
Does not provide any attainments in the professional sense

Within the scope of out-of-school activities, while some of the mentor teachers regard the performed activities as beneficial and necessary, some of them think these activities do not provide any attainments in the professional sense. MT18 stated the following; *"I think it's helpful. It's helpful, as in... You know, there is the district national education, provincial national education, other organizations who are our educational stakeholders. In the sense of getting to know those institutions, it will certainly help their professional lives in the future. In terms of knowing their functioning. Where to go in case of a need, where to meet that need, how to apply, who can help etc."* In order to indicate that performed activities were

beneficial and necessary, MT27 stated the following; *"I don't suppose that they attain anything big vocationally, I don't think so. But of course, it helps with getting to know the surroundings from a cultural point of view"* in order to indicate that what happened would be helpful culturally for getting to know the surroundings, but not professionally.

3.3 Findings Related to School Administrator Opinions

In the analysis of the data obtained as a result of semi-structured interviews conducted with school administrators; presentation of the data was similarly carried out under three titles which are attainments from in-class applications, attainments from in-school applications and attainments from out-of-school applications.

3.3.1. Attainments from In-Class Applications

Within the scope of in-class applications, school administrators have mentioned attainments such as adaptation to the school and the profession, teaching processes, student-parent communication and superior-subordinate relationship. The sub-themes under the theme of Attainments from In-Class Applications are shown in Chart 7.

Chart 7: Attainments from In-Class Applications

Duties and Responsibilities of the School Administrator
Adaptation to the school and the profession
Teaching processes
Student-parent communication
Superior-subordinate relationship

School administrators have indicated that they guided the novice teachers on subjects such as teaching duties and responsibilities of school administrators, adaptation to the school and the profession, teaching processes, student-parent communication, and superior-subordinate relationship. SA1 communicated the following; *"The initial worries of our teachers when they arrived at the school about the classroom environment, have disappeared. So when they really start teaching, they are going to be comfortable as if they have been working in this profession for years. So at least there's that psychological relief. ...They have attainments about the teaching profession, such as how to teach the student, how to attend a class, what kind of dialogue to establish with the student or the parents."* From this statement, we can understand that the novice teachers have adapted to the profession in this process, had attainments about teaching processes, and how to communicate with students and parents. SA3's statement of *"There are many deficiencies in universities, about preparing for the profession, about implementation. So these novice teacher applications provide massive attainments to novice teachers in terms of gaining experience, learning the profession, and starting out in the profession adequately."* supports the findings.

3.3.2 In-School Activities and Attainments

The sub-themes under the theme of In-School Activities and Attainments are shown in Chart 8.

Chart 8: In-School Activities and Attainments

Learning personal rights
Use of e-school and MNE data processing systems
Official correspondence rules
Ceremonial celebrations
Disciplinary board works
Salary - extra lesson calculations
Communication with students and parents
Trips
Reporting and permission procedures
Tracking attendance

School administrators expressed that novice teachers had attainments from in-school activities, on subjects such as learning of personal rights, use of e-school and NME data processing systems, official correspondence rules, disciplinary board works, salary - extra lesson calculations, communication with students and parents, trips, reporting and permission procedures, and tracking attendance. SA1's following statement supports these findings. *"They learned what their personal rights are. They learned where and who are officers, superiors, principal, students and parents. Even if there are no direct administrators, principal, vice principals, or officers in the school, they learned to do their own work, inducting themselves, how to resort to calculating salaries even if they are not able to calculate their own salary."*

3.3.3 Out-of-School Activities and Attainments

The sub-themes under the theme of Out-of-School Activities and Attainments are shown in Chart 9.

Chart 9: Out-of-School Activities and Attainments

Recognition of relevant institutions
Recognition of city culture

Within the scope of out-of-school activities, school administrators have stated that novice teachers had attainments about recognition of relevant institutions and city culture. AS1 summarized the contribution especially about recognition of city culture, with these words: *"...At least through these out-of-school trips, things such as city recognition, watching films... It may have seemed like an imposition to our friends. But when I think about teachers and myself who gave their years to this did not go to a waterfall park and watch the scenery there... Feedback from my friends was like 'Yes, I did go to Atlıhan before, but I did not know anything about Atlıhan'. They said that they went there shopping, but now they have learned why Atlıhan is Atlıhan when they were told about it there. It is positive when I consider their feedback."* AS2 stated the following about recognition of relevant institutions: *"There are institutional trips among out-of-school applications. Works have been done about familiarizing with Provincial National Education, District National Education, other official institutions, District Governorship, Registration Office and recognition of city. Of course, they have learned the functions of the institutions and organizations there. Someone*

explained them something. So they got to know the province they work in. They have been informed about city. I think they have attained the skill of reporting these."

4. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of this study were summarized under three main titles in this research which examined in-class, in-school and out-of-school attainments of novice teachers in the Induction to Teaching Program, in accordance with the opinions of novice teachers, mentor teachers and school administrators. In this section of the research, comparative discussion of the results obtained under these titles is aimed.

Novice teachers have mentioned that there were attainments on subjects such as learning-teaching process, non-schedules events and social relations. Opinions of mentor teachers were in parallel with opinions of novice teachers and supportive of obtained findings. Novice teachers stated that the attainments related to the teaching-learning process during in-class applications were as follows; receiving feedback about the teaching processes, managing the teaching process, technology use in teaching, support regarding the knowledge of the field, use of different methods - techniques, information on teaching tools and equipment, practical application, classroom management, and communication with the student. There are some evidences in the literature that mentoring improve the skills of novice teacher. (Borko & Mayfield, 1995; Fletcher & Barrett, 2004). According to Awaya and others (2003); mentor - novice teacher relationship needs to be considered as a process and there should be an equal relationship. A mentor is a guide who gives practical information and also provides moral support. Moreover, mentors should enable the novice teachers to explore themselves. Yarrow and Millwater (1997) also emphasized that efficient consultancy is a powerful vocational learning resource for employees. Daresh (2003) also emphasized the responsibilities of mentor teachers such as consultancy, guidance, setting an example and developing skills. With mentoring, the emotional and psychological support given to novice teachers develops their self-confidence, and improves their morale and satisfaction with the profession (Bullough, 2005; Lindgren, 2007; Marable & Raimondi, 2007). In addition, the guidance of mentors also help novice teachers improve their classroom management, time and workload management skills (Lindgren, 2007; Malderez, Hobson, Tracey, & Kerr, 2007); assist them with their socialization and adaptation with the norms of the school environment; and finally improves their teaching skills (Bullough & Draper, 2004; Edwards, 1998; Wang & Odell, 2002).

In this context, it is possible to say that mentor teachers have performed these roles within the scope of this research. In the research conducted by Ulubey (2017), novice teachers have stated that they received support from mentor teachers towards developing teaching skills. Also, in the research of Köse (2016) and Balkar & Şahin (2014), findings were reached towards the existence of the support provided to novice teachers by mentor teacher in terms of educational and scholastic attainments. Within the context of difficulties encountered, newly assigned teacher candidates are known to

experience problems such as planning of the teaching, selection of proper methods and techniques, evaluation of the teaching (Öztürk and Yıldırım, 2012); classroom management, efficient communication with students (Korkmaz, Saban and Akbaşlı, 2004); and motivation of students (Sarı and Altun, 2015) according to previous research. It can be said that Induction to Teaching Program supports newly assigned teachers to this end. Views of Bozak, Yıldırım and Demirtaş (2011) and Gürşimşek (1998) about observations of colleagues significantly contributing to vocational development are also supportive of the findings of the research. In the research conducted by Kozikođlu and Soyalp (2018), it was determined that attainments such as conducting applications in real class environment and gaining experience, learning classroom management, recognizing student characteristics, implementing different methods and techniques, and preparing materials were gained by novice teachers within the scope of in-class applications. Also, in the studies of Altıntaş and Görge (2016), findings about the positive aspects of the induction to teaching program were obtained, such as its inclusion of practice more than theory and contribution to the vocational development of novice teacher by mentor teachers. Similarly, in a research conducted by İlyas, Coşkun and Toklucu (2017), program was received favorably in terms of preparation for the profession and vocational development. Oral and Demir (2016) also described the novice teaching process as a preparation and guidance process. In Kaya's (2016) study, it was found that novice teachers get a chance to apply the theoretical information they learned at the university in the induction to teaching program, get a chance to see their own deficiencies especially in classroom management, learn to plan and conduct a lesson under the guidance of the mentor teacher, and learn where to use what methods and techniques by observing experienced teachers. In a lot of studies in the literature, newly assigned teachers seem to be pleased with the training applications they received and that it contributed positively to their vocational developments (Huling-Austin, 1992; Pinkston, 2008; Holloway, 2001; Thompson, Paek, Goe and Ponte, 2005; Raffel and Holbert, 2006; Lindgren, 2007; Kane (2008); Waters, 2009; Ingersoll and Strong, 2011; Mastapha, 2011, Mingo, 2012).

School administrators have indicated that, through in-class applications, novice teachers had attainments on subjects such as teaching duties and responsibilities of school administrators, adaptation to the school and the profession, teaching processes, student-parent communication, and superior-subordinate relationship. Mordan (2012) emphasizes that the help received from school principals as an educational resource plays an important role in professional commitment of newly assigned teachers. According to Griffin (1999), mentorship enables the development of new skills by increasing self-confidence of individuals. Moreover, mentors are motivated in academic sense when they help their relative colleagues and provide themselves with job satisfaction by enhancing their personal skills (Luna and Cullen, 1995). In this context, it can be said that school administrators also experience job satisfaction and are motivated through the guidance they give to novice teachers in the period of the induction to teaching program. There are findings in the studies in the literature about contribution of school principals to vocational developments of teachers (Aksoy and Işık, 2008;

Ekinci, 2010), the fact that they share knowledge through the transfer of experience (Dönmez, Uğurlu and Cömert, 2011), and setting examples and personally supporting their employees (Sezgin, Koşar and Er, 2014).

Novice teachers also talked about the existence of attainments from non-scheduled activities among in-class applications. Mentor teachers have supported this view of novice teachers by stating that novice teachers had various attainments within the scope of non-scheduled events, such as watch duty, holding PTA meetings, preparing group reports, performing club works and filling class books. Wallace (2009) expressed that induction to teaching is quite important for newly assigned teachers to adapt to the school, and the relationship between the mentor and the novice teacher structures the education process. Burks (2010) also stated that the experience and knowledge transfer between the mentor teacher and the novice teacher has positive results for both parties, and it supports vocational development. Fraizer (2006) also emphasized that the coherence between the mentor and the novice is important. In this context, non-scheduled-activity-related attainments that arise from a positive relationship established between the mentor teacher and the novice teacher contribute to adaptation to the school and the profession.

Novice teachers expressed that they had attainments from in-school activities, on subjects such as administrative tasks, e-school system, use of NME data processing systems, social event organization, surtitle writing, EBA and FATİH projects, duties of the guidance service, giving permission slips, and disciplinary board works. Mentor teachers also expressed that novice teachers had attainments from in-school activities, on subjects such as administrative tasks, e-school system, use of NME data processing systems, social event organization, surtitle writing, EBA and FATİH projects, duties of the guidance service, giving permission slips, and disciplinary board works. School administrators expressed that novice teachers had attainments from in-school activities, on subjects such as learning of personal rights, use of e-school and NME data processing systems, official correspondence rules, disciplinary board works, salary - extra lesson calculations, communication with students and parents, trips, reporting and permission procedures, and tracking attendance. Similar findings were found in the studies conducted in the literature (Gökulu, 2017; Sarıkaya, Samancı and Yılar, 2017; Kozikoğlu and Soyalp, 2018).

Within the scope of out-of-school activities, novice teachers expressed that they have visited institutions such as science and arts center, directorate of national education, public education center, guidance research center, and district governorship; they went on city trips and interviewed retired teachers within the scope of meeting with experience activities. While some of the mentor teachers regard the performed activities as beneficial and necessary, some of them think these activities do not provide any attainments in the professional sense. School administrators have stated that novice teachers had attainments about recognition of relevant institutions and city culture through out-of-school activities. To Feiman-Nemser, Carver, Schwille and Susan (1999), teachers who are new to the profession need to learn more in their first years, and therefore they need their vocational development to be planned. That's why training

applications of new and inexperienced teachers must be seen as an interdisciplinary process which includes consultancy, teaching, and influence (Cullingford, 2006). In this context, it can be said that induction to teaching program supports this interdisciplinary approach via in-class, in-school and out-of-school activities and through mentor teachers and school administrators. The findings of Kozikoğlu and Soyalp (2018) also show that they think that it is beneficial for the novice teachers to know about the institutions and where to go when they need it, through out-of-school activities. In a similar manner, İlyas, Coşkun and Toklucu (2017) have also stated in their research, that more than half of the novice teachers think that out-of-school applications are beneficial in terms of recognizing the city culture and learning about operations of different institutions.

Upon examination of the obtained findings as a whole, induction to teaching program is perceived as a positive and necessary application by novice teachers, mentor teachers, and school administrators. Both novice and mentor teachers have expressed their opinions towards the existence of significant attainments within the scope of learning - teaching, in-school activities, and out-of-school activities.

In the context of the results reached through the findings of the research, the following suggestions can be presented for the process:

- In-class applications of the induction to teaching program contributes positively to vocational development of novice teachers and must be maintained in a planned manner.
- As for in-school applications, the duties and responsibilities of school administrators should be transferred to novice teachers in a more planned and detailed way.
- Out-of-school applications must be continued in a coordinated way with relevant institutions, organizations, and people.

For further research, the following suggestions can be presented:

- "In-Service Training" aspect of the Induction to Teaching Program can be examined.
- "Evaluation" aspect of the Induction to Teaching Program can be scrutinized in depth.
- Teaching profession sufficiency of the teachers who were and were not included in the Induction to Teaching Program can be examined comparatively.
- Applications in Turkey can be comparatively analyzed with induction to teaching programs in other countries of the world.

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